

Socio-economic and clinical needs and challenges in early detection and progression monitoring of Alzheimer's Disease in primary healthcare in Greece

Pikouli Foteini Aikaterini, Psychologist, research associate of Alzheimer Hellas, foteinipikouli@hotmail.com
Holst Gitte Juel, Clinical Study Manager, Evnia ApS, Inge Lehmanns Gade 10, INCUBA NAVITAS, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark, gjh@evnia.dk
Koukoura Angeliki, Clinical Study Manager, Evnia ApS, Inge Lehmanns Gade 10, INCUBA NAVITAS, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark, anko@evnia.dk
Antonopoulou Kyriaki, Biostatistician, Evnia ApS, Inge Lehmanns Gade 10, INCUBA NAVITAS, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark, kyan@evnia.dk
Tsolaki Magda, Neurologist-Psychiatrist, LND, CIRI-AUTH, Alzheimer Hellas tsolakim1@gmail.com

Blood-based biomarkers for Alzheimer's Disease (AD) offer significant advantages over established neuroimaging and cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers [Hampel et al., 2023]. They permit earlier, faster, less invasive and more cost-effective diagnosis, while also aiding in risk evaluation, monitoring disease progression, and assessing treatment efficacy. As part of the EU-funded 2D-BioPAD project, the Greek Association of Alzheimer's Disease and Related Disorders conducted an online survey to explore the socio-economic and clinical requirements and challenges associated with blood-based (specifically plasma) AD diagnostics, particularly in primary healthcare settings across Greece. This survey was developed following a similar European study conducted within the same project. The European survey was first translated in Greek and then distributed nationwide to patients, caregivers, primary and specialized healthcare professionals, health system decision-makers, and AD biomarker experts.

The findings of this survey will provide valuable insights into the needs, concerns, and barriers to the acceptance of point-of-care in vitro diagnostic (IVD) tools for Alzheimer's disease in Greece, and will also guide future efforts within the 2D-BioPAD project.

4 key words:

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